

Z_k -Magic Labeling of Cycle of Graphs

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Abstract: For any non-trivial Abelian group A under addition a graph G is said to be A -magic if there exists a labeling $f : E(G) \rightarrow A - \{0\}$ such that, the vertex labeling f^+ defined as $f^+(v) = \sum f(uv)$ taken over all edges uv incident at v is a constant. An A -magic graph G is said to be Z_k -magic graph if the group A is Z_k , the group of integers modulo k and these graphs are referred as k -magic graphs. In this paper we prove that the graphs such as cycle of generalized peterson, shell, wheel, closed helm, double wheel, triangular ladder, flower and lotus inside a circle are Z_k -magic graphs and also prove that if G is Z_k -magic graph and n is even then $C(n.G)$ is Z_k -magic.

Key Words: A -magic labeling, Z_k -magic labeling, Z_k -magic graph, cycle of graphs, Smarandachely A -magic.

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§1. Introduction

Graph labeling is currently an emerging area in the research of graph theory. A graph labeling is an assignment of integers to vertices or edges or both subject to certain conditions. A detailed survey was done by Gallian in [6]. If the labels of edges are distinct positive integers and for each vertex v the sum of the labels of all edges incident with v is the same for every vertex v in the given graph then the labeling is called a magic labeling. Sedláček [8] introduced the concept of A -magic graphs. A graph with real-valued edge labeling such that distinct edges have distinct non-negative labels and the sum of the labels of the edges incident to a particular vertex is same for all vertices. Low and Lee [7] examined the A -magic property of the resulting graph obtained from the product of two A -magic graphs. Shiu, Lam and Sun [9] proved that the product and composition of A -magic graphs were also A -magic.

For any non-trivial Abelian group A under addition a graph G is said to be A -magic if there exists a labeling $f : E(G) \rightarrow A - \{0\}$ such that, the vertex labeling f^+ defined as $f^+(v) = \sum f(uv)$ taken over all edges uv incident at v is a constant. Otherwise, it is said to be *Smarandachely A -magic*, i.e., $|\{f^+(v), v \in V(G)\}| \geq 2$. An A -magic graph G is said to

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be Z_k -magic graph if the group A is Z_k , the group of integers modulo k . These Z_k -magic graphs are referred to as k -magic graphs. Shiu and Low [10] determined all positive integers k for which fans and wheels have a Z_k -magic labeling with a magic constant 0. Motivated by the concept of A -magic graph in [8] and the results in [7], [9] and [10] Jeyanthi and Jeya Daisy [1]-[5] proved that some standard graphs admit Z_k -magic labeling. Let G be a graph with n vertices $\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ and consider n copies of G as G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n with vertex set $V(G_i) = \{u_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$. The cycle of graph G is denoted by $C(n, G)$ is obtained by identifying the vertex u_1^j of G_j with u_i of G for $1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq n$. In this paper we study the Z_k -magic labeling of some cycle of graphs and also prove that if G is Z_k -magic graph and n is even then $C(n, G)$ is Z_k -magic. We use the following definitions in the subsequent section.

Definition 1.1 A generalized peterson graph $P(n, m)$, $n \geq 3, 1 \leq m < \frac{n}{2}$ is a 3 regular graph with $2n$ vertices $\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and edges $(u_i v_i), (u_i u_{i+1}), (v_i v_{i+m})$ for all $1 \leq i \leq n$, where the subscripts are taken modulo n .

Definition 1.2 A shell S_n is the graph obtained by taking $n - 3$ concurrent chords in a cycle C_n . The vertex at which all the chords are concurrent is called the apex.

Definition 1.3 The wheel W_n is obtained by joining the vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n of a cycle C_n to an extra vertex v called the centre.

Definition 1.4 The closed helm CH_n is the graph obtained from a helm H_n by joining each pendent vertex to form a cycle.

Definition 1.5 A double wheel graph DW_n of size n can be composed of $2C_n + K_1$, that is it consists of two cycles of size n , where the vertices of the two cycles are all connected to a common hub.

Definition 1.6 The triangular ladder graph TL_n , $n \geq 2$ is obtained by completing the ladder $P_2 \times P_n$ by adding the edges $v_{1,j} v_{2,j+1}$ for $1 \leq j \leq n$. The vertex set of the ladder is $\{v_{1,j}, v_{2,j} : 1 \leq j \leq n\}$.

Definition 1.7 The flower Fl_n is the graph obtained from a helm H_n by joining each pendent vertex to the central vertex of the helm.

Definition 1.8 A lotus inside a circle LC_n is a graph obtained from the cycle $C_n : u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n, u_1$ and a star $K_{1,n}$ with the central vertex v_0 and the end vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n by joining each u_i and $u_{i+1}(\text{mod } n)$.

§2. Main Results

Theorem 2.1 Let G be a Z_k -magic graph with magic constant b then $C(n, G)$ is Z_k -magic if n is even.

Proof For any integer $b \in Z_k$. Let v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the vertices of the cycle C_n . Let G be

any Z_k -magic graph with magic constant b . Therefore $f^+(v) \equiv b \pmod{k}$ for all $v \in V(G)$.

For any integer $a \in Z_k - \{0\}$, define the edge labeling $g : E(C(n.G)) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ as follows:

$$g(v_i v_{i+1}) = \begin{cases} a & \text{for } i \text{ is odd,} \\ k - a & \text{for } i \text{ is even,} \end{cases}$$

and $g(e) = f(e)$ for other $e \in E(C(n.G))$. Then the induced vertex labeling $g^+ : V(C(n.G)) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $g^+(v) \equiv b \pmod{k}$ for all $v \in V(C(n.G))$. Hence g^+ is constant and it is equal to $b \pmod{k}$. Notice that $C(n.G)$ admits Z_k -magic labeling when n is even, then it is therefore a Z_k -magic graph. \square

Theorem 2.2 *Let G be a Z_k -magic graph with magic constant b then $C(n.G)$ is Z_k -magic if k is even.*

Proof For any integer $b \in Z_k$. Let v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the vertices of the cycle C_n . Let G be any Z_k -magic graph with magic constant b . Therefore $f^+(v) \equiv 0 \pmod{k}$ for all $v \in V(G)$.

For any integer $a \in Z_k - \{0\}$, define the edge labeling $g : E(C(n.G)) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ to be $g(v_i v_{i+1}) = \frac{k}{2}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n-1$, $g(v_n v_1) = \frac{k}{2}$, $g(e) = f(e)$ for other $e \in E(C(n.G))$.

Then the induced vertex labeling $g^+ : V(C(n.G)) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $g^+(v) \equiv b \pmod{k}$ for all $v \in V(C(n.G))$. Hence g^+ is constant and it is equal to $b \pmod{k}$. Since $C(n.G)$ admits Z_k -magic labeling when k is even, then it is a Z_k -magic graph. \square

Theorem 2.3 *The graph $C(n.C_r)$ is Z_k -magic except r is even, n is odd and k is odd.*

Proof Let the vertex set and the edge set of $C(n.C_r)$ be $V(C(n.C_r)) = \{v_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E(C(n.C_r)) = \{v_i^j v_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r-1, i \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{v_r^j v_1^j : 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{v_1^j v_1^{j+1} : 1 \leq j \leq n-1\} \cup \{v_1^n v_1^1\}$.

Case 1. r is odd.

For any integer $a \in Z_k - \{0\}$, define the edge labeling $f : E(C(n.C_r)) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ as follows:

$$f(v_i^j v_{i+1}^j) = \begin{cases} k - a & \text{for } i \text{ is odd, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ a & \text{for } i \text{ is even, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \end{cases}$$

$$f(v_1^j v_1^{j+1}) = a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n-1,$$

$$f(v_1^n v_1^1) = a.$$

Then the induced vertex labeling $f^+ : V(C(n.C_r)) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $f^+(v) \equiv 0 \pmod{k}$ for all $v \in V(C(n.C_r))$.

Case 2. r is even.

Subcase 2.1 n is even.

The cycle C_r is Z_k -magic with magic constant zero when r is even. Therefore by theorem 2.1 it is Z_k -magic.

Subcase 2.2 n is odd and k is even.

By Theorem 2.2 it is Z_k -magic.

Hence f^+ is constant and it is equal to $0(mod k)$. Since $C(n.C_r)$ admits Z_k -magic labeling, then it is a Z_k -magic graph. \square

The example for Z_{15} -magic labeling of $C(5.C_7)$ is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Z_{15} -magic labeling of $C(5.C_7)$

Conjecture 2.4 The graph $C(n.C_r)$ is not Z_k -magic when r is even, n is odd and k is odd.

Observation 2.1 The graph $C(n.C_{n_1}, C_{n_2}, \dots, C_{n_l})$ is Z_k -magic when n_1, n_2, \dots, n_l are odd.

Theorem 2.5 The cycle of generalized peterson graph $C(n.P(r, m))$ is Z_k -magic except r is even, n is odd and k is odd.

Proof Let the vertex set and the edge set of $C(n.P(r, m))$ be respectively $V(C(n.P(r, m))) = \{u_i^j, v_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E(C(n.P(r, m))) = \{u_i^j v_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_i^j u_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r-1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_r^j u_1^j : 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{v_i^j v_{i+m}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ where the subscripts are taken modulo r .

Case 1. r is odd.

For any integer a such that $k > 3a$, define the edge labeling $f : E(C(n.P(r, m))) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ as follows:

$$f(v_i^j v_{i+m}^j) = a \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(u_i^j v_i^j) = k - 2a \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(u_i^j u_{i+1}^j) = \begin{cases} 3a & \text{for } i \text{ is odd, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ k - a & \text{for } i \text{ is even, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \end{cases}$$

$$f(u_1^j u_1^{j+1}) = k - 2a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n - 1 \text{ and } f(u_1^n u_1^1) = k - 2a.$$

Then the induced vertex labeling $f^+ : V(C(n.P(r, m))) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $f^+(v) \equiv 0 \pmod k$ for all $v \in V(C(n.P(r, m)))$.

Case 2. r is even.

Subcase 2.1 n is even.

The graph $P(r, m)$ is Z_k -magic with magic constant zero. Therefore by theorem 2.1 it is Z_k -magic.

Subcase 2.2 n is odd and k is even.

By theorem 2.2 it is Z_k -magic in this case.

Hence f^+ is constant and it is equal to $0 \pmod k$. Since $C(n.P(r, m))$ admits Z_k -magic labeling, then it is a Z_k -magic graph. \square

The example for Z_5 -magic labeling of $C(5.P(5, 2))$ is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Z_5 -magic labeling of $C(5.P(5, 2))$

Conjecture 2.6 The cycle of generalized peterson graph $C(n.P(r, m))$ is not Z_k -magic when r is even, n is odd and k is odd.

Theorem 2.7 The cycle of shell graph $C(n.S_r)$ is Z_k -magic.

Proof Let the vertex set and the edge set of $C(n.S_r)$ be respectively $V(C(n.S_r)) = \{v_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E(C(n.S_r)) = \{v_i^j v_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r - 1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{v_r^j v_1^j : 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{v_1^j v_{i+2}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r - 3, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{v_1^j v_1^{j+1} : 1 \leq j \leq n - 1\} \cup \{v_1^n v_1^1\}$. For any integer a such that $k > (r - 2)a$, define the edge labeling

$f : E(C(n.S_r)) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(v_1^j v_{i+2}^j) &= 2a \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq r-3, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ f(v_1^j v_2^j) &= f(v_r^j v_1^j) = a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ f(v_i^j v_{i+1}^j) &= k-a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r-1, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ f(u_1^j u_1^{j+1}) &= k-(r-2)a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n-1, \\ f(u_1^n u_1^1) &= k-(r-2)a. \end{aligned}$$

Then the induced vertex labeling $f^+ : V(C(n.S_r)) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $f^+(v) \equiv 0 \pmod k$ for all $v \in V(C(n.S_r))$. Hence f^+ is constant and it is equal to $0 \pmod k$. Since $C(n.S_r)$ admits Z_k -magic labeling, then it is a Z_k -magic graph. \square

The example for Z_7 -magic labeling of $C(5.S_5)$ is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Z_7 -magic labeling of $C(5.S_5)$

Theorem 2.8 *The cycle of wheel graph $C(n.W_r)$ is Z_k -magic.*

Proof Let the vertex set and the edge set of $C(n.W_r)$ be respectively $V(C(n.W_r)) = \{w_j, u_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E(C(n.W_r)) = \{u_i^j u_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r-1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_r^j u_1^j : 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{w_j u_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_1^j u_1^{j+1} : 1 \leq j \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_1^n u_1^1\}$. For any integer a such that $k > 2(r-1)a$, define the edge labeling $f : E(C(n.W_r)) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(w_j u_i^j) &= 2a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ f(w_j u_1^j) &= k-2(r-1)a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ f(u_i^j u_{i+1}^j) &= k-a \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq r-1, 1 \leq j \leq n, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(u_r^j u_1^j) &= k - a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(u_1^j u_1^{j+1}) &= ra \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n - 1, \\
 f(u_1^n u_1^1) &= ra.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then the induced vertex labeling $f^+ : V(C(n.W_r)) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $f^+(v) \equiv 0(mod k)$ for all $v \in V(C(n.W_r))$. Hence f^+ is constant and it is equal to $0(mod k)$. Since $C(n.W_r)$ admits Z_k -magic labeling, the cycle of wheel graph $C(n.W_r)$ is a Z_k -magic graph. \square

The example of Z_{13} -magic labeling of $C(5.W_7)$ is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Z_{13} -magic labeling of $C(5.W_7)$

Theorem 2.9 *The cycle of closed helm graph $C(n.CH_r)$ is Z_k -magic.*

Proof Let the vertex set and the edge set of $C(n.CH_r)$ be respectively $V(C(n.CH_r)) = \{w_j, u_i^j, x_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E(C(n.CH_r)) = \{u_i^j u_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r - 1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_r^j u_1^j : 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{x_i^j x_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r - 1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{x_r^j x_1^j : 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{w_j x_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{x_i^j u_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_1^j u_1^{j+1} : 1 \leq j \leq n - 1\} \cup \{u_1^n u_1^1\}$.

Case 1. r is odd.

For any integer a such that $k > (r + 1)a$, define the edge labeling $f : E(C(n.CH_r)) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ as follows:

$$f(u_i^j u_{i+1}^j) = \begin{cases} k - a & \text{for } i \text{ is odd, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ 2a & \text{for } i \text{ is even, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \end{cases}$$

Then the induced vertex labeling $f^+ : V(C(n.CH_r)) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $f^+(v) \equiv 0 \pmod k$ for all $v \in V(C(n.CH_r))$.

Hence f^+ is constant and it is equal to $0 \pmod k$. Since $C(n.CH_r)$ admits Z_k -magic labeling, then it is a Z_k -magic graph. \square

The example of Z_6 -magic labeling of $C(3.CH_3)$ is shown in Figure 5.

Theorem 2.10 *The cycle of double wheel graph $C(n.DW_r)$ is Z_k -magic except r is even, n is odd and k is odd.*

Proof Let the vertex set and the edge set of $C(n.DW_r)$ be respectively $V(C(n.DW_r)) = \{v_j, u_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E(C(n.DW_r)) = \{v_i v_i^j, v_i u_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{v_i^j v_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r-1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{v_r^j v_1^j : 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_i^j u_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r-1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_r^j u_1^j : 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_1^j u_1^{j+1} : 1 \leq j \leq n-1\} \cup \{u_1^n u_1^1\}$.

Case 1. r is odd.

For any integer a such that $k > 3a$, define the edge labeling $f : E(C(n.DW_r)) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(v_i v_i^j) &= 2a \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ f(v_i u_i^j) &= k - 2a \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ f(v_i^j v_{i+1}^j) &= k - a \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq r-1, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ f(u_i^j u_{i+1}^j) &= \begin{cases} 3a & \text{for } i \text{ is odd, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ k - a & \text{for } i \text{ is even, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \end{cases} \\ f(v_r^j v_1^j) &= k - a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ f(u_1^j u_1^{j+1}) &= k - 2a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n-1, \\ f(u_1^n u_1^1) &= k - 2a. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2. r is even.

Subcase 2.1 n is even.

The graph DW_r is Z_k -magic with magic constant zero. Therefore by theorem 2.1 it is Z_k -magic.

Subcase 2.2 n is odd and k is even.

By Theorem 2.2 it is Z_k -magic in this case.

Hence f^+ is constant and it is equal to $0 \pmod k$. Since $C(n.DW_r)$ admits Z_k -magic labeling, then it is a Z_k -magic graph. \square

The example of Z_9 -magic labeling of $C(5.DW_3)$ is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Z_9 -magic labeling of $C(5.DW_3)$

Conjecture 2.11 *The cycle of double wheel graph $C(n.DW_r)$ is not Z_k -magic when r is even, n is odd and k is odd.*

Obsevation 2.2 *The graph $C(n.DW_{n_1}, DW_{n_2}, \dots, DW_{n_l})$ is Z_k -magic when n_1, n_2, \dots, n_l are odd.*

Theorem 2.12 *The cycle of triangular ladder graph $C(n.TL_r)$ is Z_k -magic.*

Proof Let the vertex set and the edge set of $C(n.TL_r)$ be respectively $V(C(n.TL_r)) = \{u_i^j, v_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E(C(n.TL_r)) = \{u_i^j u_{i+1}^j, v_i^j v_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r-1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_i^j v_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r-1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_i^j v_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{v_1^j v_1^{j+1} : 1 \leq j \leq n-1\} \cup \{v_1^n v_1^1\}$.

Case 1. r is odd.

For any integer a such that $k > 2a$, define the edge labeling $f : E(C(n.TL_r)) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ as follows:

$$f(u_i^j u_{i+1}^j) = \begin{cases} 2a & \text{for } i \text{ is odd, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ k-a & \text{for } i \text{ is even, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \end{cases}$$

$$f(v_i^j v_{i+1}^j) = \begin{cases} k-a & \text{for } i \text{ is odd, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ a & \text{for } i \text{ is even, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \end{cases}$$

$$f(u_1^j v_1^j) = k-a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(u_i^j v_i^j) = a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(u_1^j v_2^j) = k - a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(u_i^j v_{i+1}^j) = k - 2a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r - 1, 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(v_1^j v_1^{j+1}) = a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n - 1,$$

$$f(v_1^n v_1^1) = a.$$

Then the induced vertex labeling $f^+ : V(C(n.TL_r)) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $f^+(v) \equiv 0(\text{mod } k)$ for all $v \in V(C(n.TL_r))$.

Case 2. r is even.

For any integer a such that $k > 2a$, define the edge labeling $f : E(C(n.TL_r)) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ as follows:

$$f(u_i^j v_{i+1}^j) = \begin{cases} 2a & \text{for } i \text{ is odd, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ k - 2a, & \text{for } i \text{ is even, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \end{cases}$$

$$f(v_i^j v_{i+1}^j) = \begin{cases} k - a & \text{for } i \text{ is odd, } i \neq (r - 1), 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ a & \text{for } i \text{ is even, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \end{cases}$$

$$f(v_{r-1}^j v_r^j) = a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(u_1^j v_1^j) = k - a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(u_i^j v_i^j) = a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r - 2, 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(u_{r-1}^j v_{r-1}^j) = k - a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(u_r^j v_r^j) = a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(u_i^j v_{i+1}^j) = k - a \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq r - 2, 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(u_{r-1}^j v_r^j) = a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n,$$

$$f(v_1^j v_1^{j+1}) = a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n - 1,$$

$$f(v_1^n v_1^1) = a.$$

Then the induced vertex labeling $f^+ : V(C(n.TL_r)) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $f^+(v) \equiv 0(\text{mod } k)$ for all $v \in V(C(n.TL_r))$. Hence f^+ is constant and it is equal to $0(\text{mod } k)$. Since $C(n.TL_r)$ admits Z_k -magic labeling, then it is a Z_k -magic graph. \square

The example of Z_{10} -magic labeling of $C(5.TL_5)$ is shown in Figure 7.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(v_j v_1^j) &= 2a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(v_j v_i^j) &= a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(v_1^j u_1^j) &= 2a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(v_i^j u_i^j) &= a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(u_1^j v_j) &= k - 2a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(u_i^j v_j) &= k - a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(v_i^j v_{i+1}^j) &= k - a \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq r - 1, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(v_n^j v_1^j) &= k - a, \\
 f(v_1^j v_1^{j+1}) &= k - a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n - 1, \\
 f(v_1^n v_1^1) &= k - a.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then the induced vertex labeling $f^+ : V(C(n.Fl_r)) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $f^+(v) \equiv 0(mod k)$ for all $v \in V(C(n.Fl_r))$. Hence f^+ is constant and it is equal to $0(mod k)$. Since $C(n.Fl_r)$ admits Z_k -magic labeling, then it is a Z_k -magic graph. \square

The example of Z_5 -magic labeling of $C(3.Fl_3)$ is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Z_5 -magic labeling of $C(3.Fl_3)$

Theorem 2.14 *The cycle of lotus inside a circle graph $C(n.LC_r)$ is Z_k -magic.*

Proof Let the vertex set and the edge set of $C(n.LC_r)$ be respectively $V(C(n.LC_r)) = \{v_j, v_i^j, u_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E(C(n.LC_r)) = \{v_j v_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{v_i^j u_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_i^j v_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r - 1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_r^j v_1^j : 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_i^j v_{i+1}^j : 1 \leq i \leq r - 1, 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_r^j v_1^j : 1 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{u_1^j v_1^{j+1} : 1 \leq j \leq n - 1\} \cup \{u_1^n v_1^1\}$.

Case 1. r is odd.

For any integer a such that $k > (r - 1)a$, define the edge labeling $f : E(C(n.LC_r)) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(v_j v_1^j) &= k - (n - 1)a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(v_j v_i^j) &= a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(v_1^j u_1^j) &= (r - 2)a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(v_i^j u_i^j) &= k - 2a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(u_i^j v_{i+1}^j) &= a \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq r - 1, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(u_r^j v_1^j) &= a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(u_i^j u_{i+1}^j) &= \begin{cases} 2a & \text{for } i \text{ is odd, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ k - a & \text{for } i \text{ is even, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \end{cases} \\
 f(u_1^j u_1^{j+1}) &= k - \frac{(r+3)a}{2} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n - 1, \\
 f(u_1^n u_1^1) &= k - \frac{(r+3)a}{2}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then the induced vertex labeling $f^+ : V(C(n.LC_r)) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $f^+(v) \equiv 0 \pmod k$ for all $v \in V(C(n.LC_r))$.

Case 2. r is even.

For any integer a such that $k > (r - 1)a$, define the edge labeling $f : E(C(n.LC_r)) \rightarrow Z_k - \{0\}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(v_j v_1^j) &= k - (n - 1)a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(v_j v_i^j) &= a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(v_1^j u_1^j) &= (r - 2)a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(v_i^j u_i^j) &= k - 2a \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(u_i^j v_{i+1}^j) &= a \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq r - 1, 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(u_r^j v_1^j) &= a \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\
 f(u_i^j u_{i+1}^j) &= \begin{cases} 2a & \text{for } i \text{ is odd, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \\ k - a & \text{for } i \text{ is even, } 1 \leq j \leq n, \end{cases} \\
 f(u_1^j u_1^{j+1}) &= k - \frac{ra}{2} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n - 1, \\
 f(u_1^n u_1^1) &= k - \frac{ra}{2}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then the induced vertex labeling $f^+ : V(C(n.LC_r)) \rightarrow Z_k$ is $f^+(v) \equiv 0 \pmod k$ for all $v \in V(C(n.LC_r))$. Hence f^+ is constant and it is equal to $0 \pmod k$. Since $C(n.LC_r)$ admits Z_k -magic labeling, then it is a Z_k -magic graph. \square

The example of Z_8 -magic labeling of $C(5.LC_5)$ is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Z_8 -magic labeling of $C(5.LC_5)$

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